

Preparation and Infrared Spectra of Chlorosubstituted o-Hydroxyacetophenone Complexes of Lanthanons

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A series of lanthanide complexes of chlorosubstituted o-hydroxyacetophenone having the composition LnL_3 where $\text{Ln} = \text{La}, ^{+3}\text{Pr}$ and Nd^{+3} is prepared. The complexes have been characterised by IR and TGA data. Tentative arrangement of three ligand molecules around central lanthanide ion is shown.

ORTHOHYDROXYPHENONES are versatile complexing agents.¹⁻³ Garg et al.⁴ reported the rare earth metal chelates with 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone. These chelates have aroused considerable importance because of their use as laser materials.^{5,6} In continuation of our previous work on proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of methylsubstituted o-hydroxyacetophenone⁷, it was considered worthwhile to study the rare earth chelates of structurally similar chlorosubstituted o-hydroxyacetophenone.

Materials and Methods; 2-Hydroxy-3-chloroacetophenone (3-Cl-2-OH-A) (m. p. 45°) and 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone (5-Cl-2-OH-A) (m. p. 50°) were prepared in the laboratory⁸. The rare-earth salts (Indian Rare earths Ltd., Udyogmandal, Kerala, India) were 99.9% pure. Infrared spectra were recorded in Laxetol mull in the region of 2 to 16 microns on Beckman IR-5 Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done by Gouy method at room temperature. The TGA thermograms were obtained with a thermobalance of Linessis, Germany. The furnace temperature, programmed for 5°C per minute, was plotted on the X-axis and the sample weight loss on the Y-axis of the X-Y recorder. For an inert atmosphere, the reaction chamber was flushed thoroughly with nitrogen. Duplicate runs were made for each complex.

Preparation of complexes:- To a solution of 1 mmole of lanthanide salt (nitrate or chloride) in ethanol-water (50% v/v) mixture, was added with vigorous stirring 3.5 mmoles of reagents dissolved in the same solvent mixture. On addition of dilute ammonium hydroxide, the precipitates were obtained. The complexes were washed with hot ethanol-water mixture and then dried at 140°.

The percentage of metal was determined and confirmed by heating the complexes slowly and then igniting to the respective oxide and weighed. The oxide thus obtained was dissolved in HCl and pH adjusted to ~ 6.0 by acetate buffer and titrated against EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator. Elemental analyses (Table 1) were performed by microanalytical techniques.

Results and Discussion

The chlorosubstituted o-hydroxyacetophenone complexes of lanthanons (Table 1) are found insoluble in water, dioxane, ethanol, etc. All these complexes are

yellow in colour. The percentage composition indicates the probable formula LnL_3 for the complexes of all the metals. This is in agreement with the reported work⁹ on the yellowish-green rare earth chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde having composition LnL_3 which are also insoluble in water and common organic solvents.

The usefulness of magnetic data to ascertain the nature of bonding in lanthanide complexes is limited¹⁰. The acetylacetonato complexes of Pr^{+3} and Nd^{+3} possess larger susceptibility than the corresponding EDTA complexes¹¹. The data (Table 1) for the magnetic moment of complexes if compared with those of the free metal ions, it is significant that comparable alterations for this series are insignificant. This is because of the fact that the 4f electrons are in no way involved in bond formation¹².

The typical thermogravimetric curves for 50 mg samples of the $\text{La}(3\text{-Cl-2OH-A})_3$ system (fig. 1) show the rapid decomposition in the region 200°-400°. This is in agreement with the reported work on rare earth acetoacetanilide.¹³ The order of decreasing heat stability is $\text{La} > \text{Pr} > \text{Nd}$. Carbonaceous residue which remains unchanged at 750° contain all the metal initially present in the chelates, suggesting non-volatilization of the chelates under the experimental conditions. Weight loss above 400° can only be due to pyrolysis of the initially

Fig. 1: The thermolysis curves of $\text{La}(3\text{-Cl-2-OH-A})_3$.

formed decomposition products. Weight losses below 200° most likely represent either slow decomposition or the loss of small amounts of occluded ligand. Metal analyses calculated from the weight of oxide remaining when the residues from the thermogravimetric runs were reheated in air to 750° also confirms the stoichiometric composition LnL_3 .

Infrared Spectra: The IR spectral data of complexes along with the ligands (Table 2) provide important information about the ligand arrangement around the metal ion. The bands in the region $700\text{--}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been identified as due to the out-of-plane bending motions of the adjacent C-H bands in aromatic hydrocarbon.¹⁴ Such bands have been observed by Rohatgi et al¹⁵ in rare earth chelates of salicylaldehyde. A very strong band at 970 cm^{-1} has been assigned to CH_3 rocking similar to the europium chelate of acetyl-acetonate.¹⁴

Fig. 2 : Arrangement of three ligand molecules around lanthanide metal.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	% of Metal		% of C		% of H		μ_{eff} BM
	found	reqd.	found	reqd.	found	reqd.	
$\text{La}(\text{3-Cl-2-OH-A})_3$	20.46	(21.46)	44.10	(44.49)	2.5	(2.7)	dia. (0)
$\text{Pr}(\text{3-Cl-2-OH-A})_3$	21.41	(21.54)	43.88	(44.37)	2.7	(2.7)	3.79 (3.58)
$\text{Nd}(\text{3-Cl-2-OH-A})_3$	21.74	(22.10)	44.10	(44.13)	2.5	(2.7)	3.70 (3.62)
$\text{La}(\text{5-Cl-2-OH-A})_3$	20.65	(21.46)	44.00	(44.49)	2.7	(2.7)	dia. (0)
$\text{Pr}(\text{5-Cl-2-OH-A})_3$	21.52	(21.54)	44.10	(44.37)	2.7	(2.7)	3.74 (3.58)
$\text{Nd}(\text{5-Cl-2-OH-A})_3$	21.71	(22.10)	43.85	(44.13)	2.6	(2.7)	3.74 (3.62)

* μ_{eff} for free metal ions are given in parentheses Ref. (11). dia. = diamagnetic.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF CHLOROSUBSTITUTED O-HYDROXYACETOPHENONES AND THEIR LANTHANIDE COMPLEXES (Values in Cm^{-1})

3-Cl-2-OH-A (5-Cl-2-OH-A)		LaL_3 (LaL_3)		PrL_3 (PrL_3)		NdL_3 (NdL_3)	
766 m	(764) m	765 m	(766) m	768 m	(763) m	764 m	(764) m
839 s	(834) s	839 s	(834) s	839 s	(834) s	833 s	(835) s
973 vs	(970) vs	970 vs	(965) vs	968 vs	(965) vs	968 vs	(968) vs
1030 w	(1030) w	1020 vw	(1026) w	1020 vw	(1026) w	1026 w	(1026) w
1125 vw	(1156) vw	1156 vw	(1152) vw	1159 vw	(1153) vw	1159 vw	(1155) vw
1227 vs	(1212) vs	1220 vs	(1217) vs	1218 vs	(1212) vs	1212 vs	(1217) vs
1250 s	(1248) s	1250 s	(1252) s	1250 s	(1252) s	1250 s	(1250) s
1315 s	(1316) s	1316 s	(1318) s	1318 s	(1316) s	1316 s	(1316) s
1658 vs	(1658) vs	1639 vs	(1639) vs	1642 vs	(1639) vs	1639 vs	(1644) vs

vw=very weak, vs=very strong, s=strong, w=weak, m=medium.

The two bands common in both the ligand as well as in the chelate at about 1026 and 1156 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-H in-plane deformation and the strong band at $1212\text{--}1227\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to C-O stretching.¹⁶ The band at 1250 cm^{-1} is assigned to C=C stretching and C- CH_3 stretching.¹⁴ The strong absorption band of all the rare earth chelates due to CH_3 symmetric bending is observed at about 1315 cm^{-1} . Such band is reported for the structurally similar spectrum of acetophenone¹⁴. The C=O stretching frequency appears at 1658 cm^{-1} which is identical to methyl substituted orthohydroxyacetophenone⁴. On chelation a shift in C=O stretching frequency provides an important information regarding the structural change. In such a situation the chelates are found to be stabilized due to resonance effect⁴ and the contribution of the canonical form is greater as compared with that in protonated chelates¹⁷⁻¹⁸.

On the basis of composition and infrared spectra the arrangement (Fig. 2) of three molecules around central metal ion is inferred.

Since no peak has been observed near 1700 cm^{-1} it can be stated that all the six oxygen atoms of the ligand are bonded directly to the metal ion.¹⁹

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References

1. M. N. PATEL and R. P. PATEL., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 1891.
2. A. AGREN., *Acta, Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 39 and 49.

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3. S. PRAKASH, Y. DUTT and R. P. SINGH., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 165.
4. C. L. GARG, K. V. NARASIMHAM and B. N. TRIPATHI., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 387.
5. A. LEMPICKI and H. SAMUELSON., *Phys. Lett.*, 1963, 4, 133.
6. M. METLAY., *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 39, 491.
7. M. N. PATEL and R. P. PATEL., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 855.
8. A. I. VOGEL., "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1956.
9. J. N. PATIL and D. N. SEN., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 413.
10. J. J. FRITZ, P. E. FIELD and I. GREENTHE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 2070.
11. S. P. SINHA., "Complexes of the Rare Earths", Pergamon, 1966.
12. T. MOELLER, D. F. MARTIN, L. C. THOMPSON, R. FERRUS, G. R. FEISTEL and W. J. RANDALL., *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.
13. A. P. BUDHKAR, P. UMAPATHY and D. N. SEN., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 376.
14. C. Y. LIANG., *Proc. Inst. Conf. on Spectroscopy, India*, 1967, 2, 302.
15. K. K. ROHATGI and S. K. SENGUPTA., *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 3061.
16. C. N. R. RAO., "Chemical Application of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, 1963.
17. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
18. K. NAKAMATO, P. J. MCCARTHY and A. C. MARTELL., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 1272.
19. D. P. GRADDON and D. G. WEEDEN., *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 247.